

Expression, purification and crystallization of pore mutants of Ammonium transport protein 1 from *Archaeoglobus fulgidus*

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ABSTRACT

Ammonium transport proteins are highly conserved families of integral membrane proteins present in all domains of life. Functional studies with members of this family have yielded controversial results with respect to the chemical identity of the transported species (NH_4^+ or NH_3) as well as to the classification of the proteins as channels or secondary active transporters. In this work different point mutations of Ammonium transport protein 1 gene (Amt-1) have been produced by site-directed mutagenesis. Then heterologous overexpression in *Escherichia coli* has been used to produce proteins and they have been purified to electrophoretic homogeneity. Crystals of Amt-1 have been obtained by sitting-drop vapor diffusion method.

KEYWORDS: ammonium transport proteins, *Archaeoglobus fulgidus*, protein purification, crystallization

1. INTRODUCTION

Archaeoglobus fulgidus is a sulfur-metabolizing anaerobe that grows optimally around 83 °C. This organism can produce biofilms when subjected to environmental stresses such as extreme pH or temperature, high concentrations of metals, or the presence of antibiotics, xenobiotics, or oxygen [1]. In the genome of *Archaeoglobus fulgidus* three homologs of Ammonium transport proteins (Amt) are present (Amt-1, Amt-2 and Amt-3).

The reasons for this Amt gene multiplicity are not yet demonstrated. It is supposed that the Amt proteins differ in their affinity to the substrate, such that the cell is able to control the ammonium uptake into the cells, as a response to environmental changes [2].

The X-ray structure of Amt-1 from *A. fulgidus* [3, 4] was initially determined at 1.54 Å. The protein shows 11 transmembrane helices per monomer. A narrow, non-continuous and mainly hydrophobic pore, located at the center of each monomer of the trimeric Amt-1, is supposed to be the substrate channel. At the extracellular channel cleft, ammonium selectivity and recruitment presumably occurs via a cation- π interaction with the side chain of W137 stabilized by hydrogen bonds to the side chain of S208. Below, F96 and F204 block the channel continuity. Further into the hydrophobic pore leading to the cytoplasm, the side chains of two highly conserved histidine residues (H157 and H305) are bridged by an H-bond. The role of these histidine residues is not yet understood.

In order to understand the structural and functional differences between these proteins and to provide new insight into the transport mechanism, we have overproduced and purified different mutants of *A. fulgidus* Amt-1.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

All chemicals have been obtained from the companies: Applichem (Darmstadt, Germany), Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany), Sigma-Aldrich (Deisenhofen, Germany) and Anatrace (Maumee, USA).

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2.1. Site-directed mutagenesis

Protocol for site-directed mutagenesis requires a small amount of the original DNA (about 300 ng) plus a forward and reverse primers of about 36 bp, containing the desired mutation in the middle (about 125 ng). dNTPs are added to a final concentration of 0.2 mM. Lastly, 0.32 μ L of PfuTurbo Polymerase (2.5 U/ μ L) is added and the reaction mixture is cycled in a PCR thermal cycler. After this step, 1 μ L of Dpn I (10 U/ μ L) restriction enzyme is added to each reaction and incubated at 37 °C for 1 h. After digestion, 1 μ L of this solution is transformed into a 50 μ L aliquot of XL-10 Gold or XL-1 Blue chemically competent cells and plated on LB agar Petri dishes. The following day one colony is picked and inoculated in 5 mL of LB medium supplemented with 100 μ g/mL ampicilline and grown at 37 °C for 10-12 hours. The desired mutation was then confirmed by sequencing using 30 ng/ μ L of purified plasmid DNA. Results were analyzed using Chromas (Technelysium).

2.2. Heterologous overexpression in *Escherichia coli* C43 (DE3) competent cells

One fresh colony of *E. coli* C43(DE3) with the desired plasmid carrying mutation of interest was taken out of an LB agar plate and inoculated into 500 mL of LB-medium, supplemented with 100 μ g/mL ampicillin and grown overnight at 37 °C with 450 rpm stirring. The following day, 20 mL of the overnight pre-culture was taken to inoculate a fresh 500 mL of LB-medium, supplemented with 100 μ g/mL ampicillin. Cell growth was monitored by measuring the optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600nm}) in culture samples of 1 mL, taken at chosen growth time points. Induction was initiated with 0.5 or 1 mM isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG). Cell growth was stopped by harvesting the cell cultures at 4 000 g, for 10 min at 4 °C (Rotor JLA-8.100). The cell pellet was collected and immediately shock frozen in liquid nitrogen for storage at -20 °C until further use for protein purification.

2.3. Protein purification

Frozen cells were resuspended in cold buffer A (20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 300 mM NaCl and 10% glycerol). At this stage, buffer A was supplemented

with a protease inhibitor cocktail mixture (Roche) to inhibit cytosolic serine, cysteine and other metalloproteases. Disruption of cells was carried out using a French Press (SLM Amicon French® Pressure Cell) or a Fluidizer (Microfluidics, M-110P). After cell disruption, cell debris is discarded by a centrifugation step of 15 min at 30 000 g at 4 °C (rotor JA-30.50). A further ultracentrifugation step, at 350 000 g (rotor 70 Ti) carried out for 60 min at 4 °C, allowed for separating the membranes from the cytoplasm. The membrane fraction was then resuspended in buffer A (10 mL per gram of membranes). For solubilization, n-dodecyl- β -D-maltopyranoside ($D_{12}DM$; CMC = 0.0087%) was added drop wise, to reach a final concentration of 1% (w/v) while stirring the membrane solution at 4 °C. Centrifugation at 350 000 g for 45 min at 4 °C was then used to separate the solubilized from the non-solubilized fractions. The solubilized fraction was then used for Ni-affinity chromatography. The $D_{12}DM$ solubilized membrane fraction was loaded onto a nickel HiTrap FF 1 mL column (GE Healthcare), pre-equilibrated with 5 column volumes of buffer A supplemented with 0.03% $D_{12}DM$. After sample loading and washing (back to baseline) in buffer A, a detergent exchange step in buffer A from 0.03% $D_{12}DM$ to 0.05% n-dodecyl-N, N-dimethylamine-Noxide (LDAO; CMC = 0.023%) was done. Consequent removal of unspecifically bound proteins from the HiTrap column material was performed by a stepwise increase of the imidazole concentration in buffer B (20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 300 mM NaCl and 10% glycerol, 0.5 M imidazole pH 8.0) to 85 mM. After washing all eluted proteins with 85 mM imidazole-containing buffer, another step increase in buffer B to 250 mM imidazole eluted the Amt-1 protein. Fractions containing Amt-1 were pooled and concentrated to a final volume of about 500 μ L in an ultrafiltration Vivaspin concentrator (Sartorius) ran at 3600 g in an Eppendorf 5810 R centrifuge. A HiTrap™ desalting column with Sephadex™ G-25 Superfine resin was consequently used to exchange the buffer of the protein sample to buffer C (20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 100 mM NaCl, 10% glycerol, 0.05% LDAO). Protein samples were collected and concentrated to a final volume of about 100-150 μ L in an ultrafiltration Vivaspin concentrator (Sartorius)

ran at 3600 g in an Eppendorf 5810 R centrifuge. Protein concentration was determined and aliquoted in 25-50 μ L before shock frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -20 $^{\circ}$ C.

2.4. Crystallization

Crystallization experiments were performed with the protein concentrated to 10 mg/mL, by vapor diffusion method in sitting drop crystallization plates. 1 μ L of protein solution was mixed with 1 μ L of precipitant solution and this mixture was equilibrated against 200 μ L of reservoir solution. The whole setup was sealed with crystal clear tape and stored at 20 $^{\circ}$ C. Crystallization plates were observed daily.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Site-directed mutagenesis

G309S (expressed and purified but not crystallized), W201A (expressed and purified but not crystallized), D149E, D149L (expressed, but not purified and crystallized), D149N (expressed, but not purified and crystallized), D149A (expressed, purified and crystallized), N205L (expressed, purified and crystallized) and T261V (expressed, purified and crystallized).

In order to explore the validation of the recruitment site, the possibility of ammonium deprotonation and re-protonation events, or the role of the C-terminus in transport control, we constructed different mutants of the Amt-1. As stated in the introduction, the remarkable conservation of two pore histidines (H157 and H305) led to the hypothesis that may play a key role in allowing the substrate to cross the central part of the channel. They might serve as proton acceptors for entering ammonium (NH_4^+) that could then traverse the central part of the channel as ammonia (NH_3) and become re-protonated on the other side. Alternatively, efficient substrate conductance might require such a narrow and mainly hydrophobic pore with a few rather precisely oriented hydrogen bond acceptor or donor functions [5].

G309 is located in the helix X together with H305. Its identity properties could again change the helix positioning and consequently the positioning of H305.

W201 is very interesting because it seems to be in a crucial position as well. It lies in helix VI together with F204 (right below, about 3.5 $\text{\AA}$ away) and may have a still unassigned, important role in the substrate transport.

D160 from AmtB has been shown to be required for transport function and is proposed to participate in ammonium binding [6]. Based on sequence homology between *E. Coli* AmtB and Amt-1 from *A. fulgidus* it has been found that D149 residue from Amt-1 is homologue to D160 from AmtB. The crystal structure of Amt-1 shows that D149 residue is located on the top of helix V (next to H157 residue). Therefore we postulated that D149 aspartat residue could have a possible structural and/or functional role by holding helix V in the right position (structural role) and at the same time D149 residue make hydrogen bond to W137 residue (functional role).

The role of residues N205 and T261 are still unclear. Computer-based simulation studies based on these two residues open an interesting question about the possible place of these two residues for protonation/deprotonation [7].

3.2. Protein purification

The purification protocol followed the guidelines that were previously established for the Amt-1 purification [8]. To decrease the interaction of

Figure 1. 12.5% SDS-PAGE of purified T261V and N205L after Ni-affinity chromatography stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue. M-protein marker (kDa).

protein impurities with the column material, further purifications were tested with different amounts of imidazole in Buffer A (5 mM, 10 mM, 15 mM, 20 mM, 25 mM, 30 mM imidazole). This, however, did not add to the final protein yields or purity levels. Purification of T261V and N205L resulted in smaller elution peaks (peak 2) from the HiTrap™ FF affinity column when compared to results obtained with wild-type Amt-1 elution peak (200 mAbs for both variants and 2000 mAbs for the wild-type, respectively). The purification process and the purity level of the protein were controlled by SDS-PAGE (Figure 1). The gel shows two bands corresponding to the dimer (60 kDa) and the monomer (33 kDa) [9]. T261V was obtained with higher purity than N205L as can be seen from the additional bands that are visible in the SDS-PAGE for the N205L protein. These contaminations could eventually be eliminated using an additional washing step between 17% and 50% of Buffer B or by gel filtration chromatography (not tried).

3.3. Crystallization

Crystals were obtained using a reservoir solution composed of 30% PEG 400, 100 mM Na-citrate pH 5.5 and 100 mM NaCl at a protein concentration of 10 mg/mL and incubated at 20 °C. 1 μ L of protein solution was mixed with 1 μ L of precipitant solution and this drop was equilibrated against 200 μ L of reservoir solution. Cubic crystals

usually appeared after 4-5 hours and grew for further 7 days. After achieving first crystals in this condition, fine screens for N205L and T261V were established to optimize the size and diffraction quality of the crystals. By varying the salt concentration (0-300 mM NaCl), the buffer concentration (100-350 mM Na-Citrate pH 5.5), the precipitant concentration (25-40% PEG 400), and protein concentration (10-20 mg/mL) bigger cubic crystals were found. The optimal condition for N205L was reached with 35% PEG 400, 0.1 M NaCl, 0.1 M Na-Citrate pH 5.5, at a concentration of 10 mg/mL protein. For the T261V variant, the optimal condition was with 35% PEG 400, 0.1 M NaCl, 0.1 M Na-citrate pH 5.5 and 15 mg/mL of protein. Flash-freezing of the crystals before data collection was done directly from the drop because the reservoir solution was already cryoprotectant.

D149A crystals appeared in a condition composed of 30% PEG 400, 100 mM Na-citrate pH 5.5, 100 mM NaCl and 100 mM Li₂SO₄ (Figure 2). Small crystals appeared after one week and grew for further three weeks. Fine screening did not help in optimizing the size of the crystals. Variations of the drop size also did not produce better results. This finding could indicate that mutating D to A at position 149 can lead to drastic changes in the tertiary structure and/or to an eventual protein instability which in turn makes it difficult to crystallize.

Figure 2. Crystals of N205L (left), T261V (middle), and D149A (right) obtained by sitting-drop vapour diffusion at 20 °C. Drop size was 1 μ L mixed with 1 μ L of 200 μ L of reservoir solution. Crystals were flash-cooled directly in liquid nitrogen. Pictures were taken under polarized light.

4. CONCLUSION

Many aspects of the biological function of Amt proteins are still poorly understood. To understand the transport mechanism of Amt proteins in general, we are using the Af-Amt-1 as a model. By combining site-directed mutagenesis and biochemical, biophysical and crystallographic methods we are investigating the validation of the recruitment site as such, the possibility of ammonium deprotonation and re-protonation events, the substrate ionic form or the role of the C-terminus in transport as well as its function in the interaction with regulatory proteins.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

This paper does not have any conflict of interest.

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